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Savez studenata Medicinskog fakulteta Novi Sad
Naučna sekcija Saveza studenata

Urednici:

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Sandra Pjevac
Ana-Marija Vejnović
Marija Ždrnja
Đurđina Radenković
Nataša Hinić
Sanja Popin
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Mila Kovačević
Bojan Radovanović
Jan Hrubik
Jelena Kosjer
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Nikola Martić
Igor Međedović

Glavni urednik:

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Urednički odbor:

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prof. dr Goran Marušić
Višnja Krizmanić
Dragica Pantić
Bojana Miljanić

Dizajn i priprema:

Milan Levnajić

Autori: Stefan Đurić, Ivica Milošević, Jelena Stolić
e-mail: stefandjuric@yahoo.com
Mentor: prof.dr Zorica Antić
 Katedra za engleski jezik, Medicinski fakultet Univerziteta u Nišu

Uvod: Engleski je postao i intranacionalni i internacionalni jezik medicinske komunikacije, osnovno sredstvo za prenos podataka i ima ulogu savremenog univerzalnog jezika, *lingua franca*.

Cilj: Cilj ovog istraživanja je da se utvrdi poznavanje formi naučnog medicinskog jezika koje se očekuju od studenata medicine, budućih lekara, kao preduslova za napredovanje u profesionalnoj karijeri.

Metode i materijali: Studija je sprovedena na Medicinskom fakultetu u Nišu i učestvovalo je 86 studenata druge godine medicine. Od studenata se zahtevalo da napišu struktuirani apstrakt, a testovi su potom analizirani i ocenjivani prema upotrebi gramatike, formalnog akademskog rečnika, upotrebe izraza za povezivanje ideja i pasusa, prema primeni i praćenju IMRAD strukture i opštem utisku.

Rezultati: Rezultati studije pokazuju da je neophdno obnavljanje opšteg engleskog jezika, naročito upotrebe relativnih zamenica, potrebno je obogaćivanje formalnog akademskog rečnika kao i povezivanje teorijskog znanja sa praktičnom primenom.

Zaključak: Interkomunikacija, učestvovanje u istraživanjima, na kongresima, praćenje novih dostignuća imperativi su u nauci uopšte, i u medicini. U ostvarivanju tog cilja od presudnog značaja je dobro poznavanje medicinskog engleskog jezika.

Gljučne reči: medicinski engleski jezik, *lingua franca*, jezik nauke

THE SCIENTIFIC IMPORTANCE OF MEDICAL ENGLISH

Authors: Stefan Đurić, Ivica Milošević, Jelena Stolić
e-mail address: stefandjuric@yahoo.com
Mentor: prof.dr Zorica Antić
 Department of English language, Faculty of Medicine University of Niš

Introduction: English has emerged as an intranational and international language of medical communications; it is a prime vehicle for the transmission of information and it is a modern *lingua franca*.

The aim: Was to determine the level of the scientific medical language the students of medicine, future doctors, are expected to have, as a precondition of their further professional development.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at the Faculty of Medicine in Nis and included 86 students. The students were asked to write a structured abstract and the tests were analyzed and graded in terms of grammar use, use of formal academic vocabulary, use of linking words, following the IMRAD structure and an overall impression.

Results: The results of our study show that students need to revise their General English knowledge, particularly the use of relative pronouns, they need to enrich their scope of formal academic vocabulary and to practice more on the application of their knowledge of language in practice.

Conclusion: Intercommunication, the participation in researching, in congresses, following new achievements are imperative in science general, and in medicine too. In realization of that aim, good knowledge of medical English is of crucial significance.

Key Words: medical English, *lingua franca*, language of science

Autor: Vanja Vajagić
e-mail adresa: vanjavajagic@yahoo.com
Mentor: doc. dr Vojislava Bugarski
 Katedra za Specijalnu rehabilitaciju i edukaciju, Medicinski fakultet Univerziteta u Novom Sadu

Uvod: Verske terapijske zajednice se izdvajaju kao sve češći terapijski modalitet u tretmanu zavisnika od psihoaktivnih supstanci. One predstavljaju svojevrsan terapijski metod kojim se utiče na bihevioralnu, psihološku, kognitivnu i socijalnu promenu među njenim klijentima.

Cilj: Cilj istraživanja je bio da se ispita uticaj boravka u verskoj terapijskoj zajednici na redukciju određenih psihopatskih obeležja.

Materijal i metode: U istraživanju je učestvovalo 59 muških ispitanika, podeljenih u tri grupe: prvu grupu od 20 ispitanika su činili zavisnici od psihoaktivnih supstanci koji borave na tretmanu u terapijskim zajednicama, drugu grupu od 20 ispitanika su činili ispitanici koji su uspešno završili tretman zavisnosti od psihoaktivnih supstanci, dok su treću grupu od 19 ispitanika činili zdravi volonteri. Tokom istraživanja korišćen je instrument za procenu psihopatije.

Rezultati: Dobijene su statistički značajne razlike između grupa na dimenzijama Antisocijalno ponašanje i Životni stil, pri čemu grupa zdravih ispitanika ostvaruje najniže prosečne vrednosti na dimenziji Antisocijalno ponašanje, zatim sledi grupa ispitanika koja je uspešno prošla tretman u terapijskoj zajednici, a zatim grupa zavisnika na lečenju. Na dimenziji Životni stil beleži se prisustvo statistički značajne razlike između grupe zdravih ispitanika i grupe ispitanika na terapijskom tretmanu, pri čemu zdravi ispitanici ostvaruju prosečno niže skorove. Grupa na terapijskom tretmanu se ne razlikuje od druge dve grupe. Na dimenzijama Interpersonalni odnosi i Psihopatski afekat nisu registrovane razlike između ispitivanih grupa.

Zaključak: Verske terapijske zajednice svojim programom utiču na redukciju antisocijalnog ponašanja u grupi ispitanika koji su uspešno završili terapijski tretman.

Gljučne reči: verska terapijska zajednica, psihopatija.

THE INFLUENCE OF BEING INCLUDED IN A THERAPEUTIC RELIGIOUS COMMUNITY ON THE REDUCTION OF PSYCHOPATHIC MARKINGS OF ADDICTS

Author: Vanja Vajagić
e-mail address: vanjavajagic@yahoo.com
Mentor: Doc. dr Vojislava Bugarski
 Department of special rehabilitation and education, Faculty of Medicine University of Novi Sad

Introduction: Religious therapeutic communities have started to stand out more often as a therapeutic model in the treatment of psycho active substance addicts. The communities present a therapeutic method which affects the behavioral, psychological, cognitive and social change among it's clients.

Aim: Aim of the research was to examine the influence of being included in a therapeutic community, on a reduction of certain psychopathic markings.

Material and methods: The total of 59 male subjects, divided into three groups: first group of 20 subjects consisted of psychoactive substance addicts being actively treated as a part of a therapeutic community; second group, of also 20 subjects, was made by individuals who have successfully finished addiction treatment on psychoactive substances, while in a therapeutic community. The third group, made of 19 subjects, was made of healthy volunteers who have never abused psychoactive substances. Psychopathic assessment instrument was used during research.

Results: Important statistical differences have appeared among tested groups in the dimensions of "Antisocial behavior" and "Lifestyle"; while the group of healthy subjects made the lowest average values of "Antisocial behavior", the group that had successfully finished therapy came second, and was followed by the group of addicts being currently treated. Statistics have also shown a great difference in the dimension of "Lifestyle" among the groups of healthy subjects and the ones currently in treatment, while the healthy subjects scored less in average.

Conclusion: Religious therapeutic communities, with their programs, affect the group of respondents that have successfully finished their therapy treatment by decreasing their antisocial behavior values.

Key words: Religious therapeutic community, psychopathy.